

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF RUSSIAN FOLKTALES IN THE FORMATION OF CHILD'S PERSONALITY IN MODERN WORLD

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ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada rus xalq ertaklarining xususiyatlari tahlil qilinadi, ertaklarning zamonaviy davrda shaxs shakllanishidagi o'рни va ahamiyati ochib beriladi, bolalarning axloqiy ma'naviy dunyosi, ijodkorligi va tanqidiy fikrlashini rivojlantirishda muhim rol o'ynaydigan ertaklarning asosiy o'ziga xos xususiyatlari ta'kidlanadi.

***Kalit so'zlar:** Xalq ertaklari, ertaklar, psixologik jihatlari, ma'naviyati, bola shaxsi, tanqidiy tafakkuri, ertak qahramonlari, xalq og'zaki ijodi.*

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье анализируются особенности русских народных сказок, раскрываются роль и значение сказки в формировании личности в современном мире. Более того, выделяются основные особенности сказки, играющие важную роль в развитии духовно-нравственного мира детей, творчества и аналитического мышления.

***Ключевые слова:** Народные сказки, волшебные сказки, психологические аспекты, духовное развитие, личность ребенка, критическое мышление, герои и героини, фольклор*

ABSTRACT

The article analyses features of Russian folktales, revealing the role and significance of fairy tales in the formation of personality in modern era, underlines main peculiarities of fairy tales that play important role in developing children's moral spiritual world, creativity and critical thinking.

Key words: *Folktales, Fairy tales, psychological aspects, spiritual, child's personality, critical thinking, heroes and heroines, folklore.*

Introduction. A fairy tale is an example of oral national Russian art that has its deepest roots in the psychology, perception, culture and language of the nation. Oral folk art is characterized as the basis in the poetics of master's creativity in art literature, as an inexhaustible source of national identity, folk worldview.¹⁶ The fantasy of fairy tales was created by the collective creative efforts of the people. It reflects the life of ordinary people and their individuality that through a fairy tale the history of thousand years is revealed. Fiction of fairy tales was created on a real basis. Any changes in the life of the people inevitably led to a changes in the content of fantastic images and their forms. There are two worlds in fairy tales and everything is ordinary here, everyday life, the weak and the strong, the rich and the poor are contrasted. The tale respects good, skillful workers, ridicules the incompetent, loafers. In a fairy tale, a person communicates with creatures that you will not meet in life: Koshchei the Immortal, Baba Yaga, the many-headed Serpent, giants, dwarf sorcerers. The ancient rulers of the nature, natural forces help or try to obstruct a person: the Sun, the Month, the Wind, the Frost, the water, the sea king, sorcerers and witches.¹⁷

Main part. Folktales consist symbolic mystery, adventures and lifelong experience that builds emotional barrier from negative impact of mental and spiritual side of society. Genre of folktale activates children's capacity of creating and dreaming, develops the ability of acting in difficult types of situations and gives them logical thinking in chains of events. Child becomes psychologically defended living in the atmosphere surrounded with love and fantasy that creates an ideal world or helps to overcome the obstacles. First - lullabies, then - pestushki¹⁸, poems and jokes.¹⁹

¹⁶ Киреева Н. В. Роль фольклорного начала в прозе Гульчеры Быковой [Электронный ресурс]. URL: http://scjournal.ru/articles/issn_1997-2911_2015_2-1_26.pdf (дата обращения: 30.04.2015)

¹⁷ <https://mylandrover.ru/salon/rol-i-znachenie-skazki-v-sovremennom-mire-znachenie-skazok-v-zhizni.html>

¹⁸ A nursery rhyme is a traditional poem or song for children

¹⁹ Ха Дык Нгюк Народная художественная культура как фактор воспитания: Дис. ... канд. пед. наук /Ха Дык Нгюк. - Мурманск, 2005.

Listening to them, the baby stays with them for life. Here, starting from a children's fairy tale begins his acquaintance with the world of literature, with the world of human relationships and with the world around him as a whole. But, why a fairy tale? When it is more logical to introduce children the real world and instructive stories "from life". Surprisingly, a fairy tale serves as a necessary stage in the mental development of a child as well as games.

Psychologists say that reading fairy tales supports children to conceive surrounding reality because of the reason that they are written in easy simple language for conception as they still do not know how to think logically, and the fairy tale does not bother with serious logical arguments. For example, children hate instructions, whereas a fairy tale does not teach him directly and has closed impact. A children's fairy tale offers colorful images that are very interesting to him, so vital information is absorbed by its imperceptibly way.

Folklore and literature are two autonomous artistic systems that have distinctive properties and at the same time closely interact with each other, forming "a certain community - literature, verbal art".²⁰ Through a fairy tale, it is easiest to explain main concepts of morality as differences between "good" and "bad". Consequently, heroes are always either good or evil, so this factor creates feeling of sympathies of the child, who identifies himself with the positive hero. Moral concepts that vividly represented in the portraits of heroes are depicted in real life and relationships with parents. For instance, if villains in fairy tales are always punished in the end, then the only way to avoid punishment is not to be a villain. The concept of good appears in a fairy tale not in the form of laws and rules, but in the form of images of strong and brave heroes, knights, princes, in the form of a kind sorceress or fairy, always ready to help. Moreover, folktales can be considered as a way of relieving anxiety of a child that can help overcome the negative aspects emerging every day.²¹ As well as, fairy tales

²⁰ Медриш Д. Н. Литература и фольклорная традиция. Вопросы поэтики 2015.

²¹ Абрашина И.В. Русские народные подвижные игры как средство воспитания нравственного поведения в процессе обучения: дис....канд. пед.наук. - СПб, 2005.

expand child's vocabulary, help to build a dialogue correctly, develop coherent logical speech and form the ability to ask questions. If fairy tales are read with good diction, clearly pronouncing all the sounds, then we have no need to visit a speech therapist.

Conclusion. Russian proverb says: "A fairy tale is a treasure of folk wisdom." Joining the fairy tale, the kid acquires a completely new type of mental activity for himself - the ability to mentally act in imaginary circumstances, and this ability is the basis for any creative activity. Fairy tales tell a ready-made fantastic story, but at the same time leave room for the imagination. A fairy tale is one of the most accessible means for developing a child's emotions, which has been used by teachers and parents at all times. In the developed modern world having digital options of books it has been forgotten that the fairy tale plays a very strong role in the developing children's personality that is why culture, traditions and language should be valued firstly. No knowledge could come ahead of the moral development of the child!

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